

MEDICAL EMERGENCIES IN DENTAL PRACTICES: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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Abstract

Medical emergencies demand immediate attention. In a dental setting, it is essential for both dentists and their staff to have the foundational knowledge necessary to recognize, assess, and manage potentially life-threatening situations until the patient can be transferred to a medical facility. The risk of mortality or severe morbidity can be minimized by ensuring the availability of basic emergency equipment and medications, as well as by ensuring that the dental team is properly trained in basic life support techniques. This article aims to provide an overview of the essential emergency medications and equipment that should be available in dental practices and to discuss the appropriate responses to some of the more common adverse medical events that may arise during dental treatments.

Key Words: Medical Emergencies, CPR, Syncope

Introduction

Medical emergency can and do occur in dental practice. Are you prepared to deal with emergencies that may arise during your workday? The best time to prepare for an emergency is well before it happens.^[1] Literature revealed that more than 54 percent of the medical emergency occurs soon after giving the local anesthesia or during the administration of the local anesthesia..^[2]

The main emphasis in the management of medical emergencies in the dental office is *preparation, prevention and management*. It has been said that “If you are prepared for the emergency, the emergency ceases to exist”.^[1]

Prevention is accomplished by conducting a thorough medical history with appropriate alterations to dental treatment as required. It is particularly important in the history to enquire about known allergies or adverse reactions to medication so that these can be avoided.^[3,4]

Preparation

Prior to discussing the management of emergency situations, it is necessary to briefly review the steps needed to fully prepare the dental office and staff so emergencies can be managed efficiently and effectively. These steps include: basic life support (BLS) training,^[5,6,7] an office emergency response team, access to emergency medical services and availability of emergency drug box and equipments. The emergency drugs with their indications and doses are summarized in table 1^[3-8]

Sr no.	Drug	Indication	Initial Adult Dose
1	Oxygen	Almost any medical emergency	100%: inhalation
2	Epinephrine	Anaphylaxis, Asthma unresponsive to albuterol/salbutamol, Cardiac Arrest	0.3–0.5 mg IM 0.3–0.5 mg IM 1 mg IV
3	Nitroglycerin	Pain of Angina	0.3–0.4 mg sublingual
4	Antihistamines diphenhydramine or chlorpheniramine	Allergic Reactions	25–50 mg IM/IV 10–20 mg IM/IV
5	Albuterol/ Salbutamol	Asthmatic Bronchospasm	2 Puffs inhalation (100 micrograms/puff)
6	Aspirin	Myocardial infarction	160–325 mg
7	Glucagon Glucose	Hypoglycemia in unconscious patient Hypoglycemia in conscious patient	1 mg IV (20% / 50% Dextrose) 15-20gms of quick acting carbohydrates eg., 4-5 glucotabs, 150-200ml fruit juice

8	Diazepam	Seizures	5 mg/ml IV
	Midazolam	Prolong seizures	10mg Buccal route
9	Hydrocortisone injection	Adrenal insufficiency Recurrent anaphylaxis	100 mg IM/IV
10	Flumazenil	Benzodiazepine Antagonist	0.2mg/min IV upto 1mg

Some of the medical equipment's required in the office are as follows^[6,7]:

1. Oxygen cylinder portable with pressure reduction valve
2. Oxygen face mask along with tubing
3. Oro pharyngeal airways of all the sizes
4. Pocket mask with oxygen port
5. Self-inflating bag and mask apparatus
6. Portable suction with appropriate suction tubing
7. Sterile syringes and needles
8. Blood glucose measurement device

Successful management of all emergency situations is dependent upon prompt recognition and effective management. A well thought out emergency plan, implemented in advance, can reduce the stress associated with the emergency to manageable levels. An in-office emergency response team should be ready consisting of not less than two people, preferably three where Member 1 (the first person to reach the emergency) stays with the victim, administers BLS as required and activates the in-office emergency team ("help!"). Member 2 brings the emergency drug kit and portable oxygen cylinder to the scene of the

emergency, while Member 3 reports the scene to emergency services to assist as necessary. ^[7,8]

Dental procedures themselves can jeopardize the airway, which must therefore be adequately protected ^[9]. The absence of a palpable pulse in an unresponsive patient indicates the need for Cardio-Pulmonary-Resuscitation(CPR) ^[10]. As per the latest Updates of American Heart Association's Guidelines for CPR and Emergency Cardiac Care 2015 ^[11,12,13]

Begin CPR by first performing chest compressions (C), followed by opening the airway (A) and delivering rescue breaths (B) (the C-A-B sequence is recommended now as compared to the former A-B-C sequence). The hands are placed on the lower half of the sternum, and chest compressions are begun at a rate of 100 to 120 compressions per minute. The goal is to depress the sternum to a depth of at least two inches allowing the chest to recoil fully on the upstroke to maintain coronary artery perfusion pressure.^[4] Thirty compressions are performed, followed by a brief pause for two rescue breaths, so a ratio of 30:2 is followed. ^[12, 13]

Compression-only CPR has been accepted as appropriate for untrained lay rescuers.^[12,13] If extenuating circumstances prohibit a healthcare provider in the out-of-hospital setting from performing rescue breathing without a barrier device, compression-only CPR should be performed until Emergency Medical Services arrive.^{[7][8]} or an Automated External Defibrillator (AED) becomes available. If an AED arrives, its pads should be applied to the front of the chest of the patient, taking care to minimize any delay in restarting chest compressions. Most modern devices verbalize further instructions after attached to the patient, AEDs will detect the current cardiac rhythm and advise whether the patient should receive defibrillation. If the AED advises a shock, cease chest compressions and stay clear of

the patient until defibrillation is completed. After defibrillation is completed, or if no shock is advised, immediately resume cycles of chest compressions and rescue breaths following the CAB sequence until additional help arrives^[11,12].

Most commonly occurring medical emergency in dental practice are as follows:^[3,4,6,13]

1. Loss of Consciousness (Syncope)
2. Hypoglycaemia
3. Postural Hypotension
4. Allergic Reaction (Anaphylaxis)
5. Adrenal Insufficiency
6. Hyperventilation
7. Foreign body obstruction
8. Status Asthmaticus
9. Status Epilepticus
10. Angina (Cardiac Pain)

Loss of consciousness (Syncope)

Signs and symptoms:

This is the most common type of medical emergency occurring in a dental set-up. ^[3] The cause of loss of consciousness in a dental practice is vasovagal syncope (fainting). If the recovery is not rapid other possibilities should be considered, such as myocardial infarction, bradycardia, heart block, stroke, hypoglycemia, or anaphylaxis. If the cause of collapse is uncertain the following steps should be taken.

Management:

The patient should be laid flat, with the legs raised in vasovagal syncope this will usually result in rapid recovery. A clear airway should be ensured and maintained and the pulse should be checked. Oxygen can be administered and let the patient in supine position only until the patient becomes conscious. To maintain the proper airway head lift chin tilt procedure can be performed. Loosening of clothes, collars or ties to maintain the airway should be done as well as use of aromatic ammonia is very much helpful in waking up the patient from the unconsciousness. ^[14]

Absence of pulse indicates cardiac arrest and cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) should start immediately. If there is a palpable pulse, hypoglycemia is a

possibility.^[4]

Hypoglycemia

Signs and symptoms:

The patient may feel nauseated, with a cold, clammy skin. There may be visual disturbance together with a feeling of dizziness. The patient's pulse will be initially rapid and weak and there may be loss of consciousness. The pulse becomes slow on recovery.

Management:

Patient should lie in the supine position with his or her legs elevated, loosen clothes so that the proper airway breathing and circulation should be maintained, oxygen administration should be done, if the patient becomes conscious or responsive give 10 to 20 mg of glucose, 15-20gms of quick acting carbohydrates eg., 4-5 glucotabs, 150-200ml fruit juice and if the patient remain in unconscious state administer glucagon 1mg through intravenous or intramuscular route.^[13]

Postural Hypotension

Postural hypotension is the second most common cause of loss of consciousness in the dental practice. ^[1,5] In any dental procedure when the patient is lying in a supine position during the treatment that may lasts for 1 to 2 hours and then suddenly the chair reclined from supine position to the stand position or when the patient stand quickly leads to a condition known as postural hypotension. ^[11-14]

Some of the other causes of postural hypotension are intake of certain drugs, prolonged convalescence period or inadequate reflex postural or during late stage of pregnancy.

Management:

If the patient is in unconsciousness, than the patient is placed in supine position only with his / her legs elevated until the patient become responsive. Proper airway should be maintained. If the patient is in consciousness state oxygen administration should be done with the help of full face mask along with the flow rate of 6 to 10 liters of oxygen per minute and if the patient is unresponsive administration of oxygen should be done with the help of bag valve mask device along with a flow rate of 10 to 15 liters per minute. ^[10-15]

Allergic reaction (Anaphylaxis)

Anaphylaxis is a systemic, life-threatening disorder considered a medical emergency with its immediate onset (seconds to minutes) and rapid progression to pulmonary, gastrointestinal, and cardiovascular systems and leading to cardiovascular and/or respiratory collapse resulting in death within minutes of inception. ^[1,16]

Management:

The immediate administration of 0.3 to 0.5 mg of epinephrine (1:1,000) I.M This may need to be repeated every 5 to 15 min. ^[12,13]

Removal of the potential triggering antigen, placing the patient in a supine position, and quickly addressing circulation-airway-breathing are critical.

In the event of respiratory distress, the patient should be placed in a position of comfort and

restrictive clothing should be removed or loosened. A short-acting β_2 agonist bronchodilator (albuterol) should be administered as 2.5 or 5 mg in 3 mL nebulized or two puffs of a metered dose inhaler every 2 to 4 hours until symptomatic relief or patient reaches a higher level of care. ^[17]

In rare cases in which rapid deterioration is occurring, epinephrine can be administered by bolus injection (0.5 to 1.0 mg or 5 to 10mL of a 1:10,000 dilution by slow IV/ IO push) or 1 mL of 1:1,000 IV/IO bolus in the event of impending or current cardiac arrest.^[14,17]

Adrenal Insufficiency

Adrenal crisis may result from adrenocortical hypofunction leading to hypotension, shock, and death. It may be precipitated by stress induced by trauma, surgery or infection. The use of supplemental steroids before dental surgery in patients at risk of an adrenal crisis is a contentious issue. The rationale for steroid supplementation is as follows. A normal physiological response to trauma is to increase corticosteroid production in response to stress.^[3] If this response is absent, hypotension, collapse and death will occur. Recent studies have suggested that dental surgery may not require supplementation.^[16] More invasive procedures however, such as third molar surgery or the treatment of very apprehensive patients, may still require cover.

Patients who may require supplementation are those who are currently taking corticosteroids or have done so in the last month. A supplement may also be required if steroid therapy has been used for more than 1 month in the previous year. If the patient

is receiving the equivalent of 20 mg Prednisolone daily then extra supplementation is not required.^[14,18]

Management:

The patient should be laid flat and 200 mg hydrocortisone sodium succinate should be administered intravenously. Ensure a clear airway and administer oxygen.^[3,19]

Hyperventilation (panic attack)

Hyperventilation is a more common emergency than is often thought. When hyperventilation persists it can become extremely distressing to the patient. Anxiety is the principal precipitating factor.

Signs and symptoms:

anxiety, light-headedness, dizziness, weakness, paraesthesia, tetany, chest pain and/or palpitations and breathlessness.

Management:

A calm and sympathetic approach from the practitioner as the diagnosis, particularly in the early stages, is not always as obvious as it may seem. Exclusion of other causes for the symptoms is of utmost importance.

Encouragement of the patient to rebreathe their own exhaled air with a paper bag placed over nose and mouth allows to increase the amount of inhaled carbon dioxide. If no paper bag is handy, the patient's cupped hands would be a (less satisfactory) alternative.

Hyperventilation leads to carbon dioxide being 'washed out' of the body, producing an alkalosis. Rebreathing exhaled air helps to return the situation to normal. ^[3,14]

Foreign Body – Upper Airway Obstruction

Severe or complete upper airway obstruction due to a foreign body rapidly progresses to unconsciousness and cardiac arrest within minutes and presents with distress, choking, coughing and cessation of breathing. [20]

Management:

Partial Obstruction: Encourage the patient to cough up or spit out. If there is poor air entry, increasing high pitched stridor or respiratory distress, manage as for complete airway obstruction.

Complete Obstruction: The victim cannot speak, breathe or cough. If he is in the dental chair sit him up, turn patient side on in chair. Support the chest with one hand and deliver five sharp back blows between the shoulder blades with the heel of the other hand. If back blows fail, five abdominal thrusts (Heimlich) should be done.

Unconscious Obstruction: Commence CPR with finger sweep between each cycle. It is important to consider cricothyroidotomy if there is no air entry at all. [20]

Status Asthmatics

The signs and symptoms of asthma include:

Breathlessness (rapid respiration – more than 25 breaths per minute), Expiratory wheezing, Use of accessory muscles of respiration and Tachycardia. In severe cases

cyanosis or slow respiratory rate (less than 8 breaths per minute), Bradycardia, Decreased level of consciousness/ confusion.

Management:

Ask the patient to sit in upright in relaxing position, loose all the tight clothing for proper airway circulation. Most attacks will respond to the patient's own inhaler, eg salbutamol (may need to repeat after 2–3 minutes). A spacer device may need to be used if the patient has difficulty using the inhaler. If the patient is distressed, urgent transport to hospital should be arranged, 10 litres per minute of oxygen should be given whilst awaiting transfer – 4–6 actuations from the salbutamol inhaler via a spacer device should be used and repeated every 10 minutes. ^[18]

Status Epilepticus

Signs and symptoms:

The patient may have an 'aura' or premonition that a seizure is about to occur; Tonic phase – loss of consciousness– patient becomes rigid and falls and becomes cyanosed. Clonic phase – jerking movements of the limbs, tongue may be bitten, frothing at the mouth, urinary incontinence. The seizure often gradually subsides after a few minutes but the patient may remain unconscious and may remain confused after consciousness has been regained.

Management of an epileptic fit :

The decision to give medication should be made if seizures are prolonged (with active convulsions for 5 minutes or more (status epilepticus) or seizures are occurring in quick

succession. If possible, high flow oxygen should be administered. The possibility of the patient's airway becoming occluded should constantly be remembered and the airway must therefore be protected. Midazolam 10 mg for adults given via the buccal or intranasal route.^[21]

Angina (Cardiac Pain)

If any sign and symptom of angina occurs in the patient, for e.g. patient says pain in the chest or says radiating pain from the chest to the shoulder, immediately stop the procedure and instead of lie the patient in the supine position make the patient to sit upright position, administer oxygen to the patient, give GTN tablet sublingually wait for 10 minutes and if the patient does not recover transfer the patient immediately to the hospital for the medical treatment.^[16,17,22]

Conclusion

Medical emergencies occurring in dental practice can be alarming. The key to minimizing the risk is taking a thorough history so that possible emergencies can be, to some extent, anticipated, and having a good working knowledge of how to manage emergencies, if they arise. Basic preparation of the office for all emergency situations is critical to the successful management of medical emergencies. It is important that each member of the dental team knows what his/her role should be in the event of a medical emergency. Training should be updated regularly and at least on an annual basis.

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